

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RINDAHL****FIRST NAME: STEVEN GLENN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCTH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: One (1)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US English

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did partially use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

Note: This document is in US letter (8.5"x11") page format

ACA-401D PERIOD 1 RESPONSE PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION – MATERIAL SUMMARY

This response paper is to the material presented in ACA-401D, period one. These materials are namely the coursepack and associated video in which MS Word “styles” are explained. The coursepack provides significant instruction on the writing expectations when writing for Euclid University. The video is a reasonably comprehensive explanation of the use of MS Word styles.

In this response paper, I intend to provide my reaction to the information learned from the styles video, the issue of plagiarism and need of citations, footnoting, matters of sentence punctuation, and American vs. English writing styles.

2) MY REACTION TO THE STUDY MATERIAL

First, as a statement regarding the course overall, I am glad this is part of the Ph.D. program of instruction. I have completed different degrees in different colleges and universities. The expectation for the writing style has never been so well documented and provided. Most frequently, there has simply been a comment, “use Turabian” or “use APA” without any further instruction. The result has been learning through trial and error. In that process, learning the style has always been, at least slightly, modified to the local usage. Having a course on how to write for Euclid is a great benefit.

In this section, I will review the five areas of lesson 1 that I found to stand out from the rest. Those are the styles video, the issue of plagiarism and need of citations, footnoting, matters of sentence punctuation, and American vs. English writing styles.

a) MS Styles

I was first introduced to the use of styles when I initiated a Ph.D. program a few years ago. In the student handbook there was a set of instructions as to the formatting of papers. These instructions included what the style settings were to be in order to match the formatting standards. No further information was provided. The result was having to search around the internet to find instructions for how to establish new settings in your styles menu. Professor Cleenewerck, on-the-other-hand, provides a clear description of what styles are, how they are reflected in the templates, and how they are used.

In the video, Cleenewerck provides a few critical pieces of information, simply in describing the styles, that are important. The one most crucial to me is (beginning at 4:12) that the “Normal” in this document is set to single-space (EUCLID 2015). I found this helpful because I expected it to be double-spaced and it seemed as if an error had occurred in the document. This small thing allowed me to relax and accept the fact that the faculty and staff of Euclid have formatted the templates the way they are for a reason and to trust the system.

The next piece of information valuable to me was the description of in-text citations (beginning at 4:30). I have never used in-text citations before, so that was an appreciated addition to my writing knowledge. It also helped convey the appropriateness of this type of notation in a simple document that may only have a few sources. Finally, from the video, there is a discussion of the differences between US and UK English formatting. I will cover those matters in the subsection below that is dedicated to the topic.

b) Plagiarism and Citations

Plagiarism seems to be a growing problem. Having known people who have intentionally and unintentionally engaged in plagiarism, resulting in damage to their academic standing and professional lives, I find this an important topic. Providing proper citations is the way to avoid any suspicion of plagiarism making citations and plagiarism two sides of one coin.

i) *Plagiarism*

The Coursepack provides a clear and concise description of plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5). The examples then provided give the reader illustration of ways one might plagiarize both intentionally (such as using another person’s ideas in a paraphrase without citation) and unintentionally (such a copy and paste from the internet). In my experience, the copy and paste from the internet seems the most frequent source of unintentional

plagiarism. It is as if people think if it is online, it is somehow public knowledge to be taken as one's own.

ii) *Citations*

Proper citations are a significant issue for me. Closely related to the problem of plagiarism, I was once accused of plagiarism when I submitted a report in a professional setting. I once faced an ethical violation accusation that could have ended the career I had at the time. I was in a panic. I knew I had not plagiarized but could not understand why those in charge could not tell that I had cited the source of the material. When I went before the ethical review committee, the portion of my work being deemed plagiarism was read. Then the person accused me, "You provided no citation for this material, which we know is from..." I asked for the copy of my work from the man who was reading it. I went to the portion he read, backed up a few sentences, and began reading, "In xyz we learn that..." I then asserted that this sentence of introduction was my citation of the source. Had I known about in-text citations, I would have never had to go through that turmoil (EUCLID 2019, 6).

c) Footnoting

I would prefer that the portion of the coursepack dedicated to footnotes was more exhaustive. When writing papers in the past the ensuring my footnotes are correct has been quite an ordeal. Having within the portion on footnotes (or in a referenced appendix) a block of examples would have been quite helpful (EUCLID 2019, 11–12).

An additional challenge is created in the body of the Coursepack, where there are a variety of footnotes (beginning on 38). None of these seem to align with each other and none seem to comply with the "Crib Sheet" guidance that. The crib sheet says, "Each footnote must begin on a new line, **indented the same amount as paragraphs in the text** (emphasis added). Footnotes are usually single-spaced, with a blank line between notes" (EUCLID 2019, 51).

d) Sentence Punctuation

I find some of the "Important Reminders" quite useful. There are matters in writing that seem must have a rule, but where or who to look up such a rule has never been an easy question. For example, reminder 6 regarding the use of a comma or colon for the sake of introducing a quote is extremely helpful (EUCLID 2019, 17). In the past, this has been a matter of my typing a quote each way and then debating with myself which way looked "more" correct and never knowing why I should choose one over the other.

The other key piece of information in the punctuation portion of the coursepack that I found helpful is the discussion of the final comma (Also known as, AKA, the “Oxford comma”) (EUCLID 2019, 19–20). While I did not find that the examples seemed to match the descriptions, I did find the descriptions to be clear and providing succinct support for the final comma. The following could be a summary statement in defense of their use:

This approach is efficient in that the INCLUSION of the final comma will never increase ambiguity in a sentence, while the EXCLUSION of the comma sometimes will. Likewise, the EXCLUSION of the comma will never increase the effectiveness of a sentence, while INCLUSION often will (EUCLID 2019, 20).¹

I appreciate the clarity of the explanation and promotion of the use of the final comma.

e) American vs. British English

As soon as I saw the title of Chapter 6 in the Table of Contents, I knew I would have to look at the chapter carefully (EUCLID 2019, 27–35). Add-in the reality that Professor Cleenewerck made a point of warning of the differences in the video and I was extra concerned to pay attention. As a matter of background, I have completed two degrees in the UK. Additionally, I was raised in a rather anglophile home where British television, brought to us by way of the local Public Broadcasting Station (PBS), was a regular part of our television viewing. The result is that in my speech and writing, I tend to be somewhat fluid between the two forms of English. I will occasionally notice that I have flowed back and forth between them. More frequently, I will not. Then I am confronted with the code-switching when the person listening confronts me with a question such as, “What is an electric fire?” Or, a proof-reader asking me why my punctuation is outside of the quote marks, or why I have the letter U in so many words where it does not belong.

In my review of this chapter, I have found two points that have the highest probability of being a problem. The first is the simple turns of phrase or word usages (such as inclusion/non-inclusion of the definite article) that are common in the UK but not in the US. For example, in the US we go to “the” hospital rather than just “go to hospital.” I believe this concern will largely be mitigated by writing in a formal academic manner.

The second point I noticed, as a potential challenge in my writing, is the use/non-use of “.” after honorifics. I do not recall when I stopped using (if I ever used) the point marker/period/full-stop after the abbreviation of a title/honorific. As a result, the use of it

¹ Here I have this justified as a block quote. In previous writing I worked under the guidance of a block quote is anything more than five lines. Furthermore, a shorter block quote, such as this one, was to be used if the block quote is complete in itself. Is eight lines of quoted text a hard and fast ruling or a general guideline?

is not only my being aware that its exclusion is a matter of British English compared to American English. In situations such as those, I can look at something after I have written it (or consider the words I used after having spoken them) and recognize either a US or UK influence. In this case, the use of the punctuation for the indicated purpose of marking an honorific abbreviation is an entirely foreign concept to me.

3) CONCLUSION

ACA-401D period one provided a great first look at the writing standards of Euclid University. The material is helpful and well organized. For me, the key things I learned in period one are related to styles video, the issue of plagiarism and need of citations, footnoting, matters of sentence punctuation, and American vs. English writing styles. The course material was effective in teaching me new material and raising my awareness of issues of which I need to be mindful.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent. "Basic ACA-401 Tutorial." *Euclid* video, 14:34. 2015. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

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